

Numerical Simulation and Model Test of Deploying Process of Tape Springs

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Abstract

The tape spring, as one type of thin-walled deployable components, boasts a small volume and lightweight when coiled. It effectively resolves the contradiction between the increasing complexity, large size, and high precision of spacecraft, and the stringent control over their dimensions and shapes by launch vehicles. In aerospace applications, it is primarily used in de-orbit sails, solar wings, and wrapped rib antennas. The driving force for its deployment originates from the elastic strain energy stored in the thin-walled shell. Prior to deployment, the tape spring is coiled around the central hub, storing elastic potential energy. Upon receiving a control command, the elastic strain energy is released, and the structure automatically deploys. The impact force generated during the deployment of the tape spring has a certain degree of influence on the satellite, making it necessary to study its deploying speed and time. This paper presents numerical simulations and experimental analyses of the deployment behavior of tape springs, focusing on their mechanical properties during motion. A numerical model was established in ABAQUS to investigate the deployment time and angular velocity during the deploying process of tape springs. Additionally, deploying tests of the tape springs were conducted in both atmospheric and vacuum environments, with high-speed photography equipment employed to record target points. Finally, the test results were compared with the numerical simulation results.

Keywords: tape spring, deployable structure, deployment behavior, numerical simulation, deploying test

1. Introduction

The tape spring is one of the most common types of thin-walled components. Due to its simple cross-section, minimal geometric parameters, and excellent deployability, it has been widely studied and applied in space deployable structures. The deployment mechanism of thin-walled deployable structures relies on the elastic strain energy stored in the thin-walled shell. The working principle involves the thin-walled structure being coiled around a central hub before deployment, storing elastic potential energy. Upon receiving a control command, the elastic strain energy is released, causing the structure to deploy. After folded, thin-walled deployable structures have small volumes and low weights, effectively resolving the conflict between spacecraft complexity, large size, and the strict dimensional and shape control required by launch vehicles. These structures find primary applications in space, including deorbit sails, solar arrays, rib-wrapped antennas, and roll-ribs antennas (Figure 1).

a) Deorbit sails

b) Rib-wrapped antennas

c) Roll-ribs antennas

Figure 1: Application of Elastic Thin-Walled Components in Aerospace[1-3]

The folding of C-shaped tape springs can be classified into two types: Equal-Sense Bending (forward folding) and Opposite-Sense Bending (reverse folding). In general, reverse folding stores more strain energy. The limit bending moment before buckling is referred to as the Peak Moment, while the bending moment after buckling is called the Steady-State Moment. Typically, the peak moment is greater than the steady-state moment. Most current research on the folding performance of C-shaped tape springs is based on Calladine's shell theory and Von Karman's large deflection theory for thin plates, where a strain energy mathematical model for the tape spring is established. The folding moment is then solved using the principle of minimum potential energy.

In recent years, many researchers have conducted in-depth studies on the deployment behavior of tape springs. Soykasap *et al.*[4] studied the application of large tape springs in ultra-thin shell deployable reflectors, proposing an optimized design to enhance the mechanical performance and stability of large tape springs. Jin *et al.*[5] explored a multi-objective optimization strategy for composite tape-spring hinges (CTSHs) by integrating numerical simulations, experimental validation, and data-driven surrogate modeling. Through iterative optimization, the study minimized overshoot angle and deployment time while considering mass constraints, providing a versatile framework for designing high-performance space deployable structures. Dewalque *et al.*[6] studied an optimization procedure for tape springs used in reflectors on small satellites, focusing on minimizing maximum stress and motion amplitude during deployment. Finite element analysis was employed to conduct parametric studies on their nonlinear mechanical behavior. Tresoldi *et al.*[7] develops two analytical models for the dynamic analysis of tape spring-based deployment in a deployable rolled-up composite antenna for CubeSats.

The models predict deployment velocity and are validated with experimental data, achieving less than 10% error in maximum speed predictions. Yan and Wu[8] investigate the non-uniform wrapping process of metallic tape springs, developing a theoretical model based on bending behavior. A finite element model in ABAQUS and experimental measurements validate the predictions, demonstrating strong agreement among theoretical, numerical, and experimental results. Oberst *et al.*[9] examined the numerical modeling and experimental validation of tape springs as representatives of thin-walled flexible structures under static and vibrational loading. Finite element simulations, combined with laser vibrometry, analyzed material properties, damping behavior, and buckling stability, highlighting the necessity of precise experimental testing for accurate stability predictions in space applications. Khan *et al.*[10] presents an experimental and finite element study of the deployment process of a composite tape spring, using a three-layered carbon fiber design. The deployment displacement is tracked experimentally, and the finite element model is validated, revealing key insights into the dynamic behavior of tape springs.

The research on tape springs has certain similarities with the study of thin-walled lenticular tubes. Hu *et al.*[11] investigated the modal behaviors, buckling, and deployment processes of composite thin-walled lenticular tubes (CTLTs) through experiments and numerical simulations. Validated against experimental results, the numerical approach effectively analyzed vibration, buckling, and the flattening and wrapping processes, offering insights into CTLT mechanical characteristics and design optimization. Chen *et al.*[12] conducted experimental and numerical investigations on the flattening and wrapping of composite thin-walled lenticular tubes. A three-dimensional ABAQUS model, accounting for geometric nonlinearity and contact effects, demonstrated high accuracy in predicting the mechanical behavior of CTLTs, validated through experimental measurements.

Tape springs are widely used in the aerospace field. Wu *et al.*[13,14] conducted surface accuracy analysis and optimization design for deployable antenna reflectors, exploring the role of tape springs in deployment strategies and optimization for wrap-rib deployable antenna.

However, current research on tape springs primarily concentrates on single springs or spring hinge, while the impact of multiple tape springs rotating and deploying together remains unclear. In practical applications, tape springs are often wound together and unfolded simultaneously, inevitably resulting in mutual contact. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to explore the establishment of a numerical model for The simultaneous deployment of multiple springs, simulate the deploying process, conduct experiments on the joint rotation and deployment of multiple springs in a vacuum box, and compare whether the deploying angular velocities and deployment time obtained from finite element simulations and experiments are consistent(Figure 2).

Figure 2: Dynamic uncoiling of multiple tape springs.

2. Numerical simulation

By using the commercially available software package ABAQUS, the finite element model is

established to simulate the dynamic uncoiling of multiple tape springs, and angular velocity are obtained. A widely used steel tape measure is chosen to act as a baseline model. The tape spring has a length of $L=500\text{mm}$ and a thickness of $t=0.123\text{mm}$ and is made from stainless steel with properties of the Young's modulus $E=200\text{ GPa}$ and Poisson's ratio $\nu=0.3$. The internal radius is $R=15.78\text{mm}$ and subtending angle is $\theta=91.58^\circ$. Tape spring are coiled 3 turns around the central hub with a radius of $R_h=10\text{mm}$ and then uncoils without gravity. The case of $n=8$ are simulated.

The coiling simulation is divided into the following steps(Figure 3):

- (1) Cylindrical flattening boards are moved inward along the radial direction of the central hub, and additional regions of tape springs are pressed to the hub, and the roots of tape springs are finally flattened and fixed on the hub.
- (2) An appropriate tension is applied to the tip of the tape spring to make the coiled part adhere to the central hub.
- (3) The central hub is turned around the central axis at an angle ψ , so that tape springs are coiled around the hub.

Figure 3: Finite element model of the coiling of multiple tape springs.

- a) Initial state. b) The roots of tape springs are flattened and fixed on the hub. c) Coiled state.

The simulation results of the coiling are extracted. The cylindrical flattening boards and guide rollers are removed, and additional regions of tape springs are fixed to the central hub, retaining the contact

conditions. The central hub is fixed and tape springs are released. The simulation results of the uncoiling are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Numerical simulation of the uncoiling of multiple tape springs.

3. Experiments

An uncoiling experiment is performed by designing an uncoiling experimental set-up and using the vacuum test chamber and the high speed image recording and processing system. A widely used steel tape measure is used in the experiment, and experimental parameters are consistent with those used in numerical simulation.

3.1. Uncoiling experimental set-up

The root of the tape spring is flattened and fixed on the central hub by screws. Multiple tape springs are coiled around the hub. The tape springs are kept coiled by metal stop rods that blocks deployed parts. The stop rods are fixed on the slide tube below(Figure 5).

Figure 5: Uncoiling experimental set-up.

In order to avoid the influence of air resistance on the uncoiling of tape springs, the experiment is carried out in a vacuum test chamber, as shown in Figure 6. The upper and front of the vacuum test chamber are glass for observation and lighting, and the side is equipped with a barometer, an air outlet valve, an air intake valve, a power interface and data interface. The air pressure in the vacuum test chamber can be pumped to -98 KPa near vacuum (-100 KPa) using vacuum pump to achieve a test environment close to no air resistance.

High speed image recording device is used to capture the motion state of tape springs during uncoiling, as shown in Figure 6. The fiducial markers are pasted on the deployed part of tape springs, the central hub and the base plate. Two high-speed cameras are used to capture the uncoiling process of tape springs synchronously from different angles.

3.2. Experimental procedures

As shown in Figure 6, the uncoiling experiment procedures are as follows:

- (1) High speed cameras are set up and the calibration frame is shot to establish a three-dimensional rectangular coordinate system.
- (2) The uncoiling experimental set-up is put into the vacuum test chamber, and is placed horizontally through a leveling instrument. Various lines are connected.
- (3) The laser timing device is turned on. The position of the laser blocking bar is adjusted and the time is cleared. Tape springs are coiled around the central hub and locked by stop rods.
- (4) The door of the vacuum test chamber is closed and locked, and the chamber is pumped to -98 KPa near vacuum by vacuum pump.
- (5) The experimental set-up is unlocked by remote control, and tape springs are released and uncoil. Meanwhile, the laser timing device is triggered to start to time.

Fiducial markers in each frame shot by the high speed camera is captured and their three-dimensional coordinates are generated through the post-processing software. The deployment time of each frame can be obtained by the number of the laser timing device in the photo. The motion of tape springs is projected onto the plane of the base plate by coordinate conversion. The uncoiling angle ψ_{EXP} of the tape spring is calculated according to the coordinates of fiducial markers. The angular velocity ω_{EXP} of the tape spring is obtained according to the deployment time and the uncoiling angle.

Figure 6: Uncoiling experiment.

4. Results

4.1. Angular velocity

The results of the angular velocity of tape springs during uncoiling obtained by two methods are compared. In numerical simulation, the curve is drawn with the uncoiling angle ψ_{FEM} and the angular velocity ω_{FEM} . In experiment, the curve is drawn with the uncoiling angle ψ_{EXP} and the angular velocity ω_{EXP} . The results of the angular velocity by two methods are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Comparison of angular velocity of tape springs during uncoiling.

4.2. Deployment time

The results of the deployment time of tape springs during uncoiling obtained by two methods are compared. In numerical simulation, the curve is drawn with the deployment time and the uncoiling angle ψ_{FEM} . In experiment, the curve is drawn with the deployment time and the uncoiling angle ψ_{EXP} . In general, the results of the two methods agree well (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Comparison of deployment time of tape springs during uncoiling.

5. Discussions

5.1. Effect of the ploy region on uncoiling

The elastic potential energy stored in the ploy region of tape springs will affect the deployment, which mainly occurs at the beginning and end of the uncoiling. If the length of the deployed part after coiling is less than the theoretical length of the ploy region, the ploy region will continue to deform and store additional elastic potential energy. At the beginning of uncoiling, the ploy region will release additional elastic potential energy to return to the normal shape, and the tape spring will also gain additional kinetic energy, affecting the prediction of the deployment. This case requires specific calculation of the elastic potential energy of the ploy region, which is not studied in this paper. At the end of uncoiling, because the root of the tape spring is flattened, the elastic potential energy in the ploy region near the root cannot be released. So the kinetic energy obtained by the tape spring will be less than expected, making the prediction of deployment inaccurate. Therefore, strictly speaking, the analytical model in this paper is applicable to the main part of the uncoiling process.

5.2. Effect of air resistance on uncoiling

In order to simulate the vacuum environment in space, the experiments in this paper are carried out in a vacuum test chamber. However, in the ordinary environment, the air resistance will affect the uncoiling process, which is related to the cross-section shape of the tape spring, the rotation direction and the air density. In this regard, uncoiling experiments in the air (0 KPa) are also conducted and compared with the results in vacuum environment (-98 KPa). The air resistance will significantly reduce the angular velocity of the tape spring.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, the deployment behavior of multiple tape springs was investigated through numerical simulations and experimental validation in a vacuum environment. A finite element model was developed to simulate the deployment process, accounting for mutual contact and dynamic interactions, while deployment experiments were also carried out. It was observed that air resistance had a notable influence on the deployment process. Additionally, the elastic potential energy stored in the ploy region influences the initial and final stages of uncoiling, affecting deployment accuracy.

While the proposed analytical model is applicable to the main deployment phase, further refinements are needed to account for these effects. Future work should focus on refining the model to incorporate the influence of the ploy region and air resistance more accurately. Additionally, investigating deployment under varying environmental conditions will further improve the reliability of tape spring-based deployable structures for space applications.

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